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A Model-Driven Approach to Secure Device Onboarding Using a Device Security Passport

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Version May 6, 2026 submitted to Comput Model Eng Sci

ABSTRACT: The evolution of the Future Mobile Internet, driven by large-scale connectivity and heterogeneous device ecosystems, introduces significant challenges for securely integrating devices into operational environments. Existing onboarding mechanisms primarily focus on authentication and credential provisioning, while security policy enforcement is typically deferred, creating a temporal gap during which devices may operate without appropriate constraints. This paper addresses this limitation by enabling policy enforcement during onboarding. To this end, we propose a model-driven approach that integrates the Device Security Passport (DSP) with the FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) protocol. The DSP is a lifecycle-aware model that aggregates heterogeneous security descriptors, including component inventories, behavioral policies, and vulnerability information, into a structured and interoperable representation. The approach leverages the FDO onboarding channel to retrieve and process DSP data at bootstrap time, enabling automated policy translation and enforcement. The method is evaluated in a realistic Smart Home environment through phase-level performance analysis. Results show that, although the proposed approach introduces an additional onboarding overhead of around 5 seconds in the evaluated scenario, this cost is incurred only once during device provisioning. Compared to manual onboarding, the approach reduces deployment time from minutes to seconds while enabling immediate policy compliance. These findings provide evidence that the proposed approach effectively bridges the gap between provisioning and enforcement with a limited performance impact in the evaluated scenario.

KEYWORDS: Secure IoT Onboarding; Future Mobile Internet Security; FIDO Device Onboard; Device Security Passport; Security Policy Enforcement; Zero-Touch Provisioning; Lifecycle Security Management

1 Introduction

The rapid evolution of the Future Mobile Internet, driven by paradigms such as 5G/6G, edge computing, and AI-enabled services, is enabling highly dynamic and large-scale interconnected ecosystems. This transformation is also reflected in the accelerated growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) market, which is projected to nearly double from \$546 billion in 2022 to \$991 billion by 2028, driven by pervasive 5G adoption, increased infrastructure investment, and AI-native IoT applications [1]. In these environments, billions of heterogeneous devices are expected to interact seamlessly across distributed and often untrusted domains.

A critical requirement in such scenarios is secure device onboarding, i.e., the process by which a device is authenticated, provisioned, and integrated into an operational environment. Existing onboarding

mechanisms, such as Device Provisioning Protocol (DPP) [2], Agile Secure Onboarding Protocol (ASOP) [3] or Bootstrapping Remote Secure Key Infrastructure (BRSKI) [4], provide secure identity establishment and ownership transfer. While these mechanisms improve usability and scalability compared to manual configuration, they focus primarily on authentication and credential provisioning, whereas security policy enforcement is typically deferred to later stages. Moreover, although approaches such as FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) [5] allow the exchange of onboarding data, the structured use of this information to enable consistent and interoperable policy enforcement during onboarding remains largely unexplored.

This separation introduces a temporal security gap, during which devices may operate with excessive privileges or without appropriate constraints. Such behavior is increasingly problematic in modern IoT deployments, especially in critical infrastructures and regulated environments where devices are expected to comply with strict security requirements from the moment they are deployed, including the secure-by-default principle emphasized in the European Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) [6].

Bridging this gap requires the ability to automatically obtain and enforce security policies at onboarding time. However, such automation fundamentally depends on the availability of structured, machine-readable security information describing the device. Without this information, policy enforcement remains manual, fragmented, or delayed, limiting scalability and consistency across heterogeneous deployments.

Structured information is already available in the form of machine-readable security descriptors, such as Software Bills of Materials (SBOMs) [7], Manufacturer Usage Descriptions (MUDs) [8], and Vulnerability Exploitability eXchange (VEX) statements [9]. However, they are inherently heterogeneous, defined using different data models, and typically produced and managed by different stakeholders across the device lifecycle. As a result, they are consumed in isolation and are not directly usable within onboarding workflows, where consistent and structured information is required to enable automated processing and policy enforcement.

To address this limitation, we propose a Device Security Passport (DSP), a machine-readable and lifecycle-aware model that enables the mapping, integration, and referencing of heterogeneous security descriptors within a unified representation. Rather than duplicating existing artifacts, the DSP provides a reference-based abstraction that preserves their semantics while enabling their coordinated use. In addition, the DSP introduces a lifecycle-aware perspective, allowing security information to evolve across manufacturing, deployment, and operation and to be progressively enriched along the supply chain.

In this paper, we address the temporal security gap in onboarding through a model-driven approach that integrates the DSP model with the FDO protocol. In this model, FDO provides secure ownership transfer and an authenticated provisioning channel, while the DSP supplies the security context required to enable automated and consistent policy enforcement. By leveraging the ServiceInfo exchange mechanism, the proposed approach follows a model-driven perspective, where machine-readable security models are automatically retrieved, processed, and enforced during onboarding, allowing devices to transition directly into a constrained and policy-compliant state.

Building upon our previous work presented at MobiSec25 [10], this extended version introduces a formalization of the DSP as a lifecycle-aware model, derived from and inspired by Open Security Controls Assessment Language (OSCAL) [11], that enables the integration and management of heterogeneous security descriptors (e.g., component inventories, behavioral policies, and vulnerability evidence) within a unified and interoperable representation. Its reference-based architecture enables the integration of external artifacts, while preserving their semantics, avoiding duplication, and supporting the progressive evolution of security information across the device lifecycle and supply chain.

The main contributions of this work are:

- The formalization of the DSP as a structured and lifecycle-aware model, derived from OSCAL, that enables the mapping, integration, and referencing of heterogeneous security descriptors, while supporting the progressive evolution of device security information across the supply chain. 73-75
- A model-driven approach that integrates DSP with the FDO protocol, enabling the retrieval and processing of structured security metadata during the onboarding process. 76-77
- The integration of automated policy enforcement at bootstrap time, leveraging DSP descriptors to bridge the gap between device provisioning and operational security. 78-79
- An experimental validation demonstrating the feasibility of the proposed approach and quantifying the performance impact of integrating DSP retrieval and policy enforcement within the FDO onboarding workflow. 80-82

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the state of the art in secure IoT onboarding and device security modelling. Section 3 presents the formal model of the Device Security Passport and its lifecycle design. Section 4 describes the proposed model-driven onboarding architecture and workflow, followed by a security analysis in Section 5. Section 6 reports the experimental validation and comparative analysis. Section 7 discusses the implications and limitations of the proposed approach, and finally, Section 8 concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work. 83-88

2 Related work 89

The secure deployment of IoT devices involves two complementary challenges. First, devices must be integrated into operational networks through automated and trusted mechanisms that establish identity, ownership, and credentials. Second, operators require structured and machine-readable security information describing device composition, behavior, and vulnerabilities in order to assess risks and enforce appropriate policies. Although significant progress has been made in both areas, onboarding protocols and security descriptors are typically addressed independently. 90-95

This section reviews the state of the art along these two dimensions: (i) secure IoT onboarding mechanisms and (ii) approaches for modelling device security information. This separation highlights a key limitation of existing solutions, namely the lack of integration between identity establishment and security context during device provisioning. 96-99

2.1 Secure IoT onboarding 100

The large-scale adoption of IoT technologies has significantly increased the complexity of securely integrating new devices into operational networks. Modern IoT deployments typically involve heterogeneous devices produced by multiple vendors, provisioned across distributed and often untrusted supply chains, and deployed with minimal human intervention. Under these conditions, traditional onboarding practices based on manual configuration, static credentials, or vendor-specific provisioning tools become difficult to scale and prone to errors [12]. Misconfigured or weakly provisioned devices may expose networks to unauthorized access or operate with excessive privileges during their initial deployment, thereby increasing the overall attack surface. 101-108

To address these challenges, secure and automated onboarding has emerged as a critical requirement for trustworthy IoT infrastructures. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) formalizes this need in its practice guide Trusted IoT Device Network-Layer Onboarding and Lifecycle Management (SP 1800-36) [13], which emphasizes that devices must receive network credentials through trusted mechanisms and that onboarding should be tightly integrated with lifecycle protections, such as device management, policy enforcement, and continuous security controls. This perspective highlights that onboarding should 109-114

not be treated solely as an authentication step, but rather as the foundation for enforcing trust and least-privilege behavior throughout the device lifetime [12].

In response, several standardized protocols and industrial solutions have been proposed to automate secure device commissioning. Approaches such as DPP [2] and BRSKI [4] aim to simplify credential distribution and reduce manual provisioning by establishing trust between devices and network domains. From an identity and credential management perspective, these approaches rely on different models to establish device identity and trust. For instance, BRSKI is based on Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) with manufacturer-installed certificates (e.g., IDevID) [14], and DPP uses elliptic-curve cryptography with bootstrapping mechanisms. Other bootstrapping approaches such as Agile Secure Onboarding Protocol (ASOP) [3] rely on pre-shared credentials, while cloud-based solutions, such as AWS IoT [15], use certificate-based models within proprietary infrastructures.

While these mechanisms improve usability and scalability compared to manual configuration, they exhibit limitations in how identity is flexibly bound to the operational domain. PKI-based approaches depend on pre-established identities, user-assisted models may impact scalability, and cloud-based solutions rely on centralized infrastructures. As a result, these approaches may limit flexibility in highly heterogeneous or geographically distributed deployments and motivate the need for more flexible identity binding mechanisms.

Among these solutions, FDO [5] has emerged as a suitable protocol for large-scale and zero-touch provisioning scenarios, addressing the limitations of existing approaches in flexible identity binding. By introducing an ownership transfer mechanism and supporting late binding, FDO enables devices to be securely associated with their operational domain at deployment time, even in untrusted environments.

This design supports secure commissioning across untrusted supply chains and allows devices to be provisioned remotely without requiring pre-installed credentials or manual intervention. Furthermore, FDO supports the secure delivery of device-specific metadata during onboarding, facilitating the integration of additional security artifacts within the provisioning workflow. The FIDO Alliance has explicitly positioned FDO as an interoperable and scalable approach aligned with the requirements identified in the NIST onboarding guide [16].

Despite these advances, these approaches primarily focus on device authentication and credential provisioning, while policy enforcement is typically addressed in separate and subsequent steps. In particular, protocols such as DPP and BRSKI enable secure onboarding and trust establishment, but do not provide native support for integrating structured security descriptors or enforcing policies during the onboarding process. Similarly, cloud-based solutions such as AWS IoT allow policy attachment during provisioning, but rely on platform-specific mechanisms and do not offer a unified, interoperable model for combining heterogeneous security artifacts. Also, although FDO provides a secure transport mechanism for onboarding data, the use of this procedure to send structured security information and enable policy enforcement during onboarding has not been fully explored.

As a result, onboarding and policy enforcement are loosely coupled, creating a temporal gap between device provisioning and the application of security controls. This limitation becomes relevant in large-scale or heterogeneous deployments, where devices may operate temporarily with excessive privileges. A more detailed comparison of representative onboarding approaches, including the proposed FDO-DSP approach, is presented in Section 6 (Table 2), where differences in automation, metadata integration, and policy enforcement capabilities are analyzed.

2.2 Security frameworks for modelling device security information

Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) has been widely applied in security systems to support abstraction, automation, and consistency in the specification of security policies and configurations [17]. These approaches rely on structured and machine-readable models to represent system behavior, security requirements, and policy enforcement rules, enabling automated processing and management [18].

In the IoT domain, similar principles have been adopted through a variety of security frameworks and models designed to represent and manage device security information across heterogeneous environments [19,20]. In practice, these approaches are often realized through machine-readable security descriptors that capture different aspects of device security. Effective IoT security therefore requires structured and interoperable representations of device security properties to support automated assessment, policy enforcement, and regulatory compliance. To this end, a wide range of security descriptors and frameworks have emerged to improve transparency regarding device composition, behavior, and risk exposure throughout the supply chain and towards operators. These descriptors provide the information necessary to evaluate trustworthiness, detect vulnerabilities, and demonstrate regulatory compliance throughout the device lifecycle.

Composition models. A first family of approaches focuses on describing what a device contains. Bills of Materials (BOMs) provide detailed inventories of device components at different layers. The most established example is the Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) [7], which enumerates software elements such as third-party libraries, firmware modules, and their associated metadata (e.g., versions, licenses, and provenance). SBOMs enable vulnerability identification by correlating components with public databases such as the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) or the National Vulnerability Database (NVD), and support software tracking and license management. Complementary efforts extend this concept to hardware and cryptographic assets. Hardware Bills of Materials (HBOMs) [21] capture physical components and their provenance to improve supply chain traceability, while Cryptographic Bills of Materials (CBOMs) [22] document cryptographic algorithms, libraries, and certificates to facilitate compliance verification and identification of weak or outdated primitives, specially in light of evolving post-quantum requirements.

Behavioral and mitigation models. Beyond internal composition, other descriptors characterize how devices are expected to behave once deployed. The Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD), standardized by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) in RFC8520 [8], specifies the intended network communication patterns through machine-readable policies that can be automatically enforced by the network infrastructure. By restricting communications to only the necessary flows, MUD reduces the attack surface of constrained devices. Extensions such as Threat MUD incorporate threat intelligence information to block communication with known malicious endpoints, enabling dynamic adaptation to emerging risks.

Vulnerability models. Additional formats address vulnerability disclosure and risk assessment. Vulnerability Disclosure Reports (VDRs) [23] enumerate known vulnerabilities that affect a product and document their severity and remediation status, while Vulnerability Exploitability eXchange (VEX) statements [9] clarify whether specific vulnerabilities are actually exploitable in a given deployment context. Together, these descriptors help reduce false positives and provide more actionable information to operators and auditors.

Standardized frameworks. To facilitate interoperability and automated processing, broader frameworks have been proposed to structure and exchange security information. The Security Content Automation Protocol (SCAP) [24] has long supported automated vulnerability assessment and configuration checking through specifications such as Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE), Common Platform Enumeration (CPE), and Extensible Configuration Checklist Description Format (XCCDF). More recently,

OSCAL [11] introduces extensible machine-readable models to represent security controls, assessments, and compliance artifacts in a consistent manner across systems and organizations. Compared with other frameworks, OSCAL has gained increasing attention due to its extensible data models and interoperability-oriented design, which facilitate the integration of heterogeneous security evidence. Several European initiatives, such as EUROSCAL¹ and the ECSO OSCAL task force², are currently promoting OSCAL as a common format for security and compliance automation. However, one of its main challenges is the initial learning curve and the need for organizations to adapt their existing processes to integrate OSCAL effectively. This transition can require significant time and resources, especially for organizations that are heavily reliant on traditional methods.

Despite the availability of these descriptors and frameworks, security information is typically produced and managed in isolation. Composition inventories, behavioral policies, and vulnerability reports are often distributed across separate formats and repositories, requiring ad-hoc integration and manual correlation during deployment. This fragmentation limits automation and complicates their direct use within onboarding workflows, motivating the need for unified approaches that can aggregate and transport heterogeneous security descriptors in a consistent and lifecycle-aware manner.

A more detailed comparison of these security descriptors and frameworks, including their capabilities and limitations, is presented in Section 6 (Table 3), which further motivates the need for unified and lifecycle-aware approaches such as the proposed DSP.

3 The Device Security Passport as a Lifecycle Security Model

To bridge the gap identified in the previous section, we introduce the DSP, a unified and lifecycle-aware model designed to aggregate heterogeneous security descriptors and make them directly consumable during device onboarding and operation. Rather than treating security information as a collection of independent artifacts, the DSP provides a structured and interoperable container that enables consistent representation, exchange, and update of device security data across the supply chain and throughout the device lifecycle.

The DSP design is grounded in OSCAL models, which are structured into three main layers that support the definition, implementation, and assessment of security controls. The *Control Layer* defines standardized control catalogs and profiles (e.g., NIST SP 800-53 or ISO/IEC 27001). The *Implementation Layer* describes how these controls are realized within a system, through models such as component definitions and system security plans. The *Assessment Layer* captures the evaluation of security posture, including observed findings, risks, and mitigation actions, typically represented through models such as the Plan of Action and Milestones (POA&M).

¹ <https://euroscal.eu/>

² <https://ecs-org.eu/?publications=actions-beyond-words-automating-audits-for-streamlined-cybersecurity-compliance-in-europe>

Figure 1: OSCAL layers and models

While this layered architecture provides a comprehensive framework for structuring security information, OSCAL remains system-centric and does not explicitly address device-level lifecycle management or the integration of heterogeneous security descriptors within onboarding workflows. In particular, it does not define how security artifacts are bound to individual devices, how they evolve across the device lifecycle, or how they can be directly consumed during provisioning. Moreover, the richness and flexibility of OSCAL models often introduce a level of complexity that may hinder their direct adoption.

The DSP addresses these limitations by introducing a device-centric and lifecycle-aware abstraction that simplifies the use of structured security information in IoT environments. In particular, it builds upon existing OSCAL models by selectively adopting those elements that are most relevant to device lifecycle management, while extending them to enable the integration of heterogeneous security descriptors and to support emerging regulatory requirements such as the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA).

This selective reuse allows the DSP to leverage the expressive power and interoperability of OSCAL, while tailoring its structure to support the binding of security artifacts to individual devices, the evolution of security information across lifecycle stages, and the mapping of external descriptors into a unified representation. In addition, the DSP avoids redundancy by not duplicating OSCAL information that is already provided by external descriptors, relying instead on structured references to maintain consistency and reduce data duplication.

As a result, the DSP provides a consistent and lightweight model that facilitates the practical use of security metadata during onboarding and operation.

The following subsections detail and formalize the DSP, while Section 4 describes its integration within the onboarding workflow.

3.1 Structural Representation

From a structural perspective, the DSP is organized into several key sections derived from and aligned with existing OSCAL models. Rather than adopting OSCAL as-is, the DSP selectively reuses and adapts elements from different OSCAL layers and models, primarily the POA&M, Component Definition, and Assessment models. This selective reduction addresses the inherent complexity of OSCAL and improves its practical applicability. In addition, the DSP avoids redundancy by not duplicating OSCAL information already provided by external security descriptors (e.g., SBOM, MUD, or VEX).

A DSP is uniquely identified and structured through four main elements: a global identifier, metadata, a system identifier, and a set of local definitions capturing device security information. This structure is formalized as follows.

Let D denote the set of devices. For each device $d \in D$, the Device Security Passport is defined as the structured tuple

$$DSP(d) = \langle U, M, S_{id}, L_d \rangle \quad (1)$$

where U is a universally unique identifier (UUID) that unambiguously identifies the passport, M represents the metadata, S_{id} denotes the system identifier binding the passport to a specific physical device, and $L_d = \{C, A, O, R\}$ captures the local definitions describing the device security posture.

These elements are derived from and aligned with OSCAL models, but are selectively simplified to retain only the information required for the DSP. The *UUID* (U) and *metadata* (M) reuse common structures present across all OSCAL models. The UUID is intended to be a machine-oriented, globally unique identifier (e.g., RFC 4122 [25]) that can be used to reference this DSP elsewhere. The metadata element captures the contextual information required to identify, version, and track the evolution of the DSP. It includes descriptive attributes (e.g., title and version), temporal information (e.g., publication and last modification timestamps), and structured revision histories that record updates together with their associated context. To support accountability and governance, metadata also defines roles and associated parties (e.g., manufacturers, integrators, operators), together with their responsibilities. This establishes a foundation for access control and coordinated lifecycle management across stakeholders. Finally, metadata supports references to external documentation through links, facilitating integration with complementary information or artifacts. The *System ID* (S_{id}) is derived from the POA&M model and establishes a verifiable binding between the logical passport and the physical device through globally unique identifiers and associated cryptographic material.

The *local definitions* section aggregates elements originating from multiple OSCAL models. In particular, *components* are aligned with both the POA&M and Component Definition models, *assessment assets* are derived from the POA&M and Assessment Plan models, while *observations* and *risks* follow the structure defined in the Assessment Results model. For clarity, a simplified excerpt of the DSP structure is shown below, where only representative fields are included and additional elements are omitted for brevity:

Listing 1: Simplified DSP structure

```
{
  "uuid": "714210d2-f8df-448c-be3e-e2213816cf79",
  "metadata": {
    "title": "SmartBulb generic DSP",
    "version": "1.0",
    "last-modified": "2026-03-01T13:57:28",
    "dsp-model-version": "1.0",
    "links": [
      {"rel": "EU conformity", "href": "..."}
    ],
    "roles": [...],
    "parties": [...],
    "responsible-parties": [...]
  },
  "system-id": {
    "identifier-type": "UUID",
    "id": "123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426614174000"
  },
  "local-definitions": {
    "components": [...],

```

```

"assessment-assets": {
  "components": [...],
  "assessment-platforms": [...]
},
"observations": [...],
"risks": [...]
}
}

```

As mentioned before, the DSP adopts a reference-based architecture in which security artifacts such as SBOM, MUD, or VEX documents are linked rather than embedded, preserving their original structure and ownership. Let \mathbb{D}_{sec} denote the domain of security descriptors analyzed in Section 2:

$$\mathbb{D}_{sec} = \mathbb{D}_{BOM} \cup \mathbb{D}_{BEH} \cup \mathbb{D}_{VUL} \cup \mathbb{D}_{MIT} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbb{D}_{BOM} includes inventory descriptors such as SBOM, HBOM, or CBOM, \mathbb{D}_{BEH} includes behavioral descriptors such as MUD profiles, \mathbb{D}_{VUL} includes vulnerability evidence descriptors such as VEX or VDR, and \mathbb{D}_{MIT} includes mitigation descriptors. These artifacts are incorporated into the DSP through structured references within the local definitions $L_d = \{C, A, O, R\}$, each capturing a specific aspect of the device security state. The integration follows a mapping aligned with the semantics of each descriptor type. In particular, composition and behavioral descriptors (e.g., SBOM, HBOM, MUD) are associated with components, vulnerability descriptors (e.g., VEX, VDR) are linked to risks, and mitigation artifacts (e.g., Threat MUD) are incorporated within the risk representation. Assessment-related outputs are captured through observations and associated assets. We now describe how these elements are formally represented.

Let $C(d)$ denote the set of components associated with device d :

$$C(d) = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\} \quad (3)$$

Each component c_i is described by a set of attributes and properties such as its UUID, type, title, description, purpose and status, and by a set of links \mathcal{L}_i . OSCAL information regarding ports and protocols has been removed, as it is already present in the MUD file.

The set \mathcal{L}_i encodes references to external security descriptors in $\mathbb{D}_{BOM} \cup \mathbb{D}_{BEH} \subset \mathbb{D}_{sec}$, thereby associating each component with its composition and expected behavior. Formally, each reference is defined as $\mathcal{L}_i = \{(href_k, rel_k, media_type_k)\}$, where $href_k$ identifies the external artifact, rel_k specifies the relationship between the component and the referenced descriptor, and $media_type_k$ indicates the format of the referenced artifact, enabling its correct interpretation and processing. Listing 2 illustrates how SBOM and MUD descriptors are linked to a component.

Listing 2: Component linking SBOM and MUD descriptors

```

{
  "components": [{
    "uuid": "comp-1",
    "type": "software",
    "props": [{"name": "vendor", "value": "ACME"}],
    "links": [
      {"rel": "SBOM", "href": "...", "media-type": "application/vnd.spdx+json"},
      {"rel": "MUD", "href": "...", "media-type": "application/mud+json"}
    ]
  }]
}

```

}

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The set $A(d)$ captures assessment assets, including tools and auxiliary components used during security evaluations or mitigation processes. The set $O(d)$ represents observations derived from these assessments, providing structured evidence and references to external reports. Together with the set of risks $R(d)$, these elements are aligned with the OSCAL assessment model, from which the DSP adopts its representation of assessment results and security findings.

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Listing 3: Example of assessment assets

```

{
  "assessment-assets": {
    "components": [{}],
    "assessment-platforms": [
      {"uuid": "3f7a6c8e-1111-45b9-9ae8-4c6b1b7a9f8e", "title": "CT-SAST"}]
    },
  "observations": [{
    "uuid": "0c4de4fc-9bde-46af-b6fe-3b5e78194dcf",
    "title": "Buffer overflow detected",
    "description": "...",
    "methods": ["TEST"],
    "origins": [{...}],
    "subjects": [{...}],
    "relevant-evidence": [{...}],
    "collected": "2026-01-02T12:14:16",
    "expires": "2026-06-02T12:14:16"
  }],
  "risks": [{
    "uuid": "8b8bae66-b28c-4fa5-9a20-b79e7322fc00",
    "title": "CVE-2024-7392",
    "description": "...",
    "links": [
      {"rel": "VEX", "href": "...", "media-type": "application/vnd.cyclonedx+xml"}],
    "status": "remediating",
    "origin": [{...}],
    "threat-ids": [{...}],
    "characterizations": [{...}],
    "deadline": "2026-10-02T12:14:16",
    "remediations": [{
      "uuid": "d28873f7-...",
      "lifecycle": "planned",
      "title": "Vendor response",
      "description": "Mitigation via Threat MUD.",
      "props": [{"name": "type", "value": "accept"}],
      "links": [
        {"rel": "Threat MUD", "href": "...", "media-type": "application/mud+json"}
      ]
    }],
    "risk-log": {...},
    "related-observations": [...]
  }],
}

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The set $R(d)$ models security risks associated with the device and its components. Each risk is defined as $r_j = \langle \mathcal{P}_{r_j}, \mathcal{L}_{r_j}, \text{Rem}_{r_j} \rangle$, where \mathcal{P}_{r_j} represents intrinsic properties of the risk (e.g., description, status, threat id) following the OSCAL assessment model, and $\mathcal{L}_{r_j} \subset \mathbb{D}_{VUL}$ contains references to vulnerability evidence (e.g., VEX, VDR), linking each risk to externally maintained vulnerability information.

Each risk may include a set of remediation actions $\text{Rem}_{r_j} = \{rem_1, \dots, rem_k\}$, which describe how the identified risk can be mitigated. Each remediation is defined as $rem_k = \langle \mathcal{P}_{rem_k}, \mathcal{L}_{rem_k} \rangle$, where $\mathcal{L}_{rem_k} \subset \mathbb{D}_{MIT}$ contains references to mitigation descriptors (e.g., Threat MUD profiles), enabling the association of risks with enforceable mitigation strategies.

This reference-based structure allows the DSP to integrate heterogeneous security artifacts within OSCAL, maintaining their original structure and semantics without duplicating their content.

3.2 Credential and Identity Representation

Device identity in the DSP is grounded in existing OSCAL models, in particular the POA&M model, from which the *System ID* element is reused. Rather than redefining identity mechanisms, the DSP leverages this construct to bind security information to individual device instances. The UUID uniquely identifies the passport itself, while the System ID provides the identifier of the physical device. In the DSP, this element establishes a verifiable association between the logical passport and the corresponding device instance.

Credential-related information is not directly embedded within the DSP, but referenced through external descriptors integrated in the model. In particular, cryptographic information can be described through linked artifacts such as CBOMs within the component block, while device authentication relies on existing onboarding mechanisms and associated credentials.

In addition, the DSP structure allows representing onboarding-related information, including credentials or bootstrap data, through the components block when required. This provides the flexibility to incorporate provisioning-specific information without modifying the core model, while keeping such data explicitly separated from the generic security descriptors. A detailed example on how to embed FDO data is described in Section 4.

3.3 Lifecycle Model

Unlike static or monolithic security descriptors, the DSP is conceived as a dynamic and incremental model that evolves together with the device it represents. As devices progress from manufacturing to integration and finally to operational deployment, their ownership context, configuration, and risk exposure naturally change. Consequently, security information must also evolve while preserving traceability and consistency. The DSP follows this progression by continuously enriching the device's security profile over time rather than replacing it.

The DSP distinguishes three types of instances of Equation 1 corresponding to different stages of the device lifecycle: a manufacturer-defined generic passport (*genDSP*), an instance passport bound to a specific device (*IDSP₁*), and an operational passport maintained during deployment (*IDSP₂*). These instances are not independent documents but successive refinements of the same structure, where each layer adds contextual information to the previous one, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: DSP lifecycle

The **Generic DSP (genDSP)** acts as a baseline that describes static and general security information about a product. It is created by the manufacturer during the design and development phase and contains generic descriptors applicable to all devices of the same model. The genDSP is digitally signed to guarantee authenticity and version-controlled to maintain historical traceability as vulnerabilities are disclosed or patches are released.

$$genDSP = \langle U_g, M_g, \emptyset, L_{d,g} \rangle \quad (4)$$

As devices move through the supply chain, the **Instance DSP (IDSP₁)** binds the generic passport to a specific physical device by introducing the system identifier S_{id} . This can be represented as a function:

$$instantiate : genDSP \times S \rightarrow IDSP_1$$

$$IDSP_1 = instantiate(genDSP, S_{id}) \quad (5)$$

so that $IDSP_1 = \langle U_{i1}, M_{i1}, S_{id}, L_{d,i1} \rangle$. This relation allows multiple instance passports to be derived from the same generic passport, each corresponding to a different device. To avoid duplication of information, the instance passport references the generic passport in the metadata (links) section, and only describes new modifications applicable to that device instance. In practice, $IDSP_1$ acts as the bridge between manufacturer-controlled information and deployment-specific contexts.

During operation, devices may diverge from their initial configuration due to updates, software extensions, hardware changes, or contextual security findings. The **Operational DSP (IDSP₂)** captures this evolution by extending $IDSP_1$ with updated components, policies, observations, and vulnerabilities identified during runtime.

$$IDSP_2 = copy(IDSP_1) \quad IDSP_2 = \langle U_{i2}, M_{i2}, S_{id}, L_{d,i2} \rangle \quad (6)$$

Maintained by integrators or operators, this layer supports active security management and enforcement, for example by supplying policy information to network controls or contextual risk data to monitoring systems. At the same time, relevant findings can be fed back to the manufacturer to improve the generic baseline and provide mitigations, enabling a continuous feedback loop across the lifecycle. Operational updates are incorporated over time as $IDSP_2^{t+1} = IDSP_2^t \oplus \Delta_t$, where \oplus denotes a merge operation that updates existing descriptors and integrates contextual information, including observations

and security findings collected during device operation. This progressive enrichment of descriptors across the lifecycle leads to a hierarchical relationship between passport types, where each stage accumulates additional security information:

$$genDSP \subset IDSP_1 \subset IDSP_2 \quad (7)$$

As devices approach end-of-life, the DSP further serves as a comprehensive historical record of security-related events and actions. This accumulated evidence supports secure decommissioning procedures, such as revoking credentials and certificates, and facilitates audits, post-incident investigations, and compliance assessments. The passport also documents support periods and update availability, providing clear visibility into maintenance responsibilities and residual risks.

Overall, the three-layer DSP design provides a continuous and evolving representation of device security across its lifecycle. By progressively enriching a shared baseline with instance-level and operational evidence, the model maintains coherence while accommodating change. This lifecycle-aware approach embeds transparency, risk assessment, and security decision-making directly into device management processes, fostering trust among supply chain stakeholders.

3.4 Storage and Retrieval of the DSP

The storage and retrieval of DSP documents are supported by a dedicated platform, referred to as the Device Security Passport Platform (DSPP), which manages DSP instances and enables controlled access across stakeholders.

From a design perspective, the DSPP acts as a repository where DSP documents are created, stored, updated, and retrieved. Manufacturers generate the generic (*genDSP*) and instance (*IDSP₁*) passports, which are stored and made accessible through the platform. In contrast, the operational passport (*IDSP₂*), containing deployment-specific information, is maintained by the device operator and may be managed outside the manufacturer-controlled environment. This separation reflects the different ownership and sensitivity of lifecycle data.

DSP retrieval is integrated into the onboarding process. During provisioning, the device provides a reference to its associated DSP, which is then retrieved, validated, and processed by the operator domain. This mechanism enables the use of up-to-date security information at bootstrap time without requiring full data embedding within the device. The reference-based design also improves scalability and avoids duplication of security artifacts.

In addition to onboarding-driven retrieval, DSPs can also be accessed independently through the platform by authorized stakeholders. Access permissions can be granted through external identity and access management mechanisms (e.g., Front-end Access Management, FEAM³), enabling controlled and role-based access to DSP documents outside the onboarding process. This supports manual inspection, auditing, and lifecycle management activities.

Access to DSP documents is governed by role-based mechanisms enforced by the DSP platform, leveraging metadata associated with each DSP instance (*roles* and *parties*) and external identity and access management components (e.g., FEAM). This enables fine-grained and role-based access control

³ <https://iotac.eu/the-roadmap-of-feam-the-front-end-access-management-system/>

across multiple stakeholders, ensuring that each entity can only access the information relevant to its responsibilities.

From a privacy and data protection perspective, the DSP model follows a data minimization approach. Security artifacts are referenced rather than embedded, allowing sensitive information to remain controlled repositories. Additionally, access restrictions ensure that only the necessary subset of information is disclosed to each entity.

Integrity and authenticity are ensured through the use of digital signatures applied at different stages of the DSP lifecycle. Each DSP instance is signed by the entity responsible for its creation or modification, enabling verification of both its origin and its content prior to use. In particular, the generic passport ($genDSP$) and the instance passport ($IDSP_1$) are signed by the manufacturer, while the operational passport ($IDSP_2$) is signed by the device operator after incorporating contextual updates. Formally, the integrity conditions for each passport type are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Integrity(genDSP) &\Leftrightarrow VerifySignature_{mfg}(genDSP) \\
 Integrity(IDSP_1) &\Leftrightarrow VerifySignature_{mfg}(IDSP_1) \\
 Integrity(IDSP_2) &\Leftrightarrow VerifySignature_{op}(IDSP_2)
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

This mechanism ensures that any retrieved DSP can be verified before being consumed, preventing tampering, and enabling trusted use of security information during onboarding and operation.

4 Model-Driven Secure Onboarding

The proposed approach for model-driven onboarding is based on the FDO protocol and the usage of the DSP. While FDO provides a cryptographically secure, zero-touch ownership transfer and an authenticated provisioning channel that supports late binding, the DSP is obtained during the FDO onboarding, extracting the security policies to be enforced before the device has access to the network. The next subsections provide an overview of the FDO protocol, and the architecture and flows we envision for the model-driven secure onboarding.

4.1 FDO Foundations

As discussed in Section 2, FDO provides a standardized mechanism for secure and zero-touch device onboarding. In this work, FDO is used as the underlying protocol to establish a trusted communication channel and a verifiable ownership context between the device and the operator.

FDO enables devices to be provisioned with a uniform set of onboarding credentials during manufacturing and later commissioned into different operational environments through a late binding process. The protocol relies on cryptographic identity and ownership evidence, allowing secure onboarding across distributed and potentially untrusted supply chains.

The onboarding process is organized into a manufacturing-time initialization phase (Device Initialization, DI) followed by a sequence of transfer-of-ownership protocols (TO0–TO2). During the DI phase, the *Manufacturer* provisions the *Device* with onboarding credentials and rendezvous information at manufacturing time. In the TO0 protocol, the *Owner* registers ownership metadata with the *Rendezvous Service*, enabling late binding between devices and operational domains. Subsequently, in the TO1 protocol, the *Device* contacts the *Rendezvous Service* to discover the appropriate *Owner* endpoint. Finally, in the TO2 protocol, the *Device* and the *Owner* perform mutual authentication and establish a secure and encrypted communication channel, which is then used to deliver configuration data and provisioning artifacts.

A key capability of FDO for this work is the *ServiceInfo* exchange model, executed over the protected TO2 channel. *ServiceInfo* enables the structured and secure delivery of configuration data and external artifacts during onboarding. In the proposed approach, this mechanism is leveraged to retrieve and transport the Device Security Passport, enabling security descriptors to be available immediately after bootstrap.

4.2 FDO-DSP Integration

While FDO provides a secure mechanism for device authentication and ownership establishment, it does not define how security policies or device-specific security descriptors are delivered and enforced during onboarding. As discussed in Section 2, this separation often leads to fragmented workflows in which policy enforcement is performed after onboarding, potentially leaving devices temporarily over-privileged.

To address this limitation, this work combines the FDO onboarding protocol with the DSP, enabling the delivery and activation of security descriptors as part of the bootstrapping process. In this model, FDO acts as a secure transport and trust establishment layer, while the DSP provides a structured and machine-readable representation of the device security state.

The integration is realized through the *ServiceInfo* exchange mechanism executed during the TO2 protocol. Once a secure channel is established between the *Device* and the *Owner*, the device provides a reference to its associated DSP (e.g., an identifier provisioned during manufacturing). The *Owner* uses this reference to retrieve the DSP from a trusted repository and verifies its integrity before processing its contents.

Once retrieved, the DSP provides access to structured security descriptors $L_d = \{C, A, O, R\}$, including component inventories, behavioral policies, and security findings. These descriptors can be immediately consumed by enforcement mechanisms within the operator domain, enabling policy-driven configuration at bootstrap time.

A key enabler of this process is the consistent binding between the device identity used in FDO and the system identifier defined in the DSP model. Let S_{id} denote the system identifier of a device in Equation 1. In the proposed approach, S_{id} is aligned with the FDO device identity $S_{id} \equiv GUID_{FDO}$, ensuring that the retrieved DSP corresponds unambiguously to the authenticated device.

In addition to security descriptors, the DSP also captures onboarding-related information required during the FDO process. Since part of the FDO protocol execution is performed by the device itself (e.g., discovery and ownership transfer), the device can be modeled as exposing an onboarding capability.

This capability is represented within the DSP using a dedicated component $c_{fdo} \in C(d)$:

$$c_{fdo} = \langle \mathcal{P}_{fdo}, \mathcal{L}_{fdo} \rangle \quad (9)$$

where \mathcal{P}_{fdo} describes the properties of the onboarding service, and \mathcal{L}_{fdo} contains references to onboarding-related artifacts. In particular, \mathcal{L}_{fdo} includes references to the Ownership Voucher as well as to network-related descriptors (e.g., MUD profiles) that define how the device can reach the Rendezvous service during the discovery phase.

To illustrate how this integration is realized in practice, Listing 4 presents a simplified excerpt of an $IDSP_1$ highlighting the elements relevant for FDO-based onboarding.

Listing 4: Integration of FDO data in the $IDSP_1$

```
{
  "system-id": { "identifier-type": "urn:fdo:device-id",
                "id": "EDBA506B90E1420298485E91160CB16F" },
```

```

"components": [
  {
    "type": "this-system",
    "title": "Home Assistant",
    "links": [
      { "rel": "CBOM", "media-type": "application/vnd.spdx+json", "href": "..."},
      { "rel": "MUD", "media-type": "application/mud+json", "href": "..."}
    ]
  },
  {
    "type": "service",
    "title": "FDO device onboard",
    "links": [
      { "rel": "ownership-voucher", "media-type": "application/cbor", "href": "..."}
    ]
  }
]
}

```

In this example, the *system-id* is aligned with the FDO device identity, ensuring a direct binding between the authenticated device and its corresponding DSP instance. The component definition includes references to external security artifacts (e.g., CBOM), while onboarding functionality is modeled as a dedicated component with references to FDO-specific artifacts such as the Ownership Voucher. The inclusion of a MUD descriptor further enables the specification of network-level policies, and should include rules to allow communication with the FDO RV service during the discovery phase.

By modeling the onboarding functionality as a component within the DSP, both security descriptors and onboarding metadata are integrated into a unified structure. This avoids the need for additional data models and ensures that all required information can be retrieved and processed through standard DSP mechanisms. The proposed model reduces the gap between authentication and policy enforcement. Devices transition directly from an unauthenticated state to a controlled and policy-compliant posture, without requiring additional manual configuration steps.

4.3 Architecture

The proposed architecture is guided by a set of design principles. First, a clear *separation of concerns* is established between identity provisioning and secure communication (handled by FDO) and security policy representation (handled by the DSP). This separation allows both layers to evolve independently while remaining tightly coupled during onboarding. Second, the architecture adopts a *reference-based design*, where security artifacts (e.g., SBOM, MUD, vulnerability reports) are not embedded but retrieved dynamically through DSP references. This improves scalability, avoids data duplication, and enables independent lifecycle management of security artifacts. Finally, the system follows a *secure-by-design onboarding paradigm*, in which policy enforcement is integrated into the onboarding workflow. By leveraging the FDO ServiceInfo exchange, security descriptors are retrieved and processed before the device becomes operational, removing the temporal gap between provisioning and enforcement.

It is assumed that the FDO protocol provides a secure channel for device authentication and ownership transfer, and that DSP instances are stored in a trusted platform (DSPP) and protected through digital signatures, allowing their integrity and authenticity to be verified prior to use. The DSP platform is expected to be reachable during onboarding, as it is required to retrieve the security descriptors associated with the

device. Finally, enforcement points within the operator domain are assumed to be capable of translating and applying the policies derived from DSP descriptors. The architecture is designed to fail securely. In case these assumptions are not met, such as DSP unavailability or verification failures, the system prevents the device from reaching a fully operational state, ensuring that no device is deployed without validated security descriptors.

The architecture defines explicit trust boundaries across its components to minimize the exposure of sensitive operations. The *operator domain* is considered the primary trusted environment, as it performs critical functions such as DSP retrieval, signature verification, descriptor processing, and policy enforcement. The *DSP platform* is trusted to provide authentic and integrity-protected DSP instances, although access to its content is controlled through authorization mechanisms. In contrast, the *rendezvous service* is treated as a minimally trusted component, as it only supports device discovery and redirection and does not participate in the secure communication channel or access sensitive data. The *device* is assumed to be trustworthy with respect to its hardware root of trust and stored credentials, but is not trusted to enforce global security policies beyond its local capabilities. The *manufacturer domain* is trusted to generate correct initial DSP instances and onboarding credentials, but is not involved in operational policy enforcement. This explicit separation confines sensitive operations to trusted domains and limits the role of external entities, thereby reducing the attack surface and strengthening the overall security posture.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the architecture is structured into three main domains: the *Manufacturer domain*, the *Intermediary platform*, and the *Operator domain*, together with the *Device*, which acts as an edge entity interacting across these domains.

Figure 3: DSP-based onboarding architecture

Manufacturer domain. The manufacturer domain hosts the *manufacturer repository* containing external security artifacts referenced by the *genDSP*, such as BOMs, MUD profiles, or vulnerability reports. These resources are not embedded in the DSP but are instead accessed through references, preserving their original structure and enabling independent lifecycle management.

The Intermediary platform acts as a trust broker between domains and hosts the DSP Platform (DSPP), which manages the storage, versioning, and controlled access to DSP instances.

Intermediary platform. The intermediary platform hosts the DSP platform (*DSPP*), which manages the storage, versioning, and controlled access to *genDSP* and *IDSP₁*. It also includes the FDO Rendezvous Server (*RV Server*), which supports device discovery by mapping device identities to operator endpoints during the TO1 phase. This platform does not participate in secure provisioning or policy enforcement, but facilitates coordination across domains.

Operator domain. The Operator domain represents the target deployment environment and concentrates the core orchestration logic of the system. It orchestrates the transition from device

authentication to policy enforcement, ensuring that security controls are applied immediately after onboarding. It includes the following key components:

- The *Owner Server*, which executes the FDO TO2 protocol, authenticates the device, and establishes the secure communication channel.
- The *DSP Manager*, responsible for retrieving $IDSP_1$ from the DSPP using the reference received via ServiceInfo, verifying its integrity, and extracting relevant descriptors.
- The *Policy Manager*, which processes the extracted descriptors and translates them into enforceable configurations.

Device. The Device acts as an active participant in the onboarding process, executing the *FDO client* and exposing its onboarding capability as part of the DSP component model. It stores onboarding credentials and the DSP reference in hardware-backed *secure storage* (e.g., TPM or secure element), ensuring protection against extraction or tampering. During onboarding, the device autonomously performs discovery and ownership transfer, and provides the DSP reference via the ServiceInfo exchange. Policy enforcement may also be applied locally through a device-side *policy enforcer*, as part of the overall system workflow.

4.4 Secure Onboarding Workflow

From a system perspective, the proposed approach follows a structured onboarding and enforcement pipeline spanning multiple domains. As illustrated in Figure 4, the workflow captures the end-to-end data flow across the Manufacturer, Intermediary, Device, and Operator domains, while Algorithm 1 formalizes the corresponding logic. The process begins with device provisioning and DSP association at manufacturing time, continues with device discovery and secure channel establishment through the FDO protocols (TO0–TO2), and culminates in the retrieval, verification, and processing of the DSP within the operator domain. Finally, the system supports continuous adaptation by retrieving updates of the DSP throughout the device lifecycle.

Figure 4: DSP-based data flow

4.4.1 Phase 1 – Device initialization and DSP association

Before deployment, each device is provisioned with onboarding credentials and bound to its corresponding security passport instance. As shown in Figure 4, during the Device Initialization (DI) phase, cryptographic credentials and rendezvous information are securely stored within the device, establishing its hardware root of trust.

In parallel, the manufacturer derives an instance-level passport ($IDSP_1$) from the generic model ($genDSP$) by binding it to the unique system identifier S_{id} of the device, as defined in Section 3. The resulting $IDSP_1$ is registered in the DSP platform, which returns a unique reference (Ref_{IDSP_1}). This reference is embedded in the device and is securely stored together with the onboarding credentials, ensuring a one-to-one association between the physical device and its corresponding passport instance since manufacturing.

Algorithm 1 Model-Driven Secure Onboarding with DSP Integration

Require: Device d with unique identifier S_{id} and FDO credentials C_{fdo} , and an associated generic DSP model $genDSP$

- 1: **Phase 1: Device Initialization and DSP Association**
- 2: Generate $IDSP_1 \leftarrow instantiate(genDSP, S_{id})$
- 3: $Ref_{IDSP_1} \leftarrow Register(IDSP_1)$
- 4: Provision device with C_{fdo} and Ref_{IDSP_1}
- 5: Make $IDSP_1$ accessible to the operator domain
- 6: **Phase 2: Discovery (TO0-TO1)**
- 7: // TO0: Owner-side registration
- 8: $OV \leftarrow ExtractVoucher(IDSP_1)$
- 9: $RV \leftarrow ExtractRVlocation(IDSP_1)$
- 10: TO0_Register($RV, OV, OwnerEndpoint$)
- 11: // TO1: Device-side discovery
- 12: $OwnerAddr \leftarrow TO1_Discover(d, RV)$
- 13: **if** $OwnerAddr = \emptyset$ **then**
- 14: **Abort** (Discovery failed)
- 15: **end if**
- 16: **Phase 3: Ownership Transfer (TO2)**
- 17: $Session \leftarrow EstablishSecureChannel(d, OwnerAddr, C_{fdo})$
- 18: **if** $Session$ not established **then**
- 19: **Abort**
- 20: **end if**
- 21: **Phase 4: DSP Retrieval and Verification**
- 22: // Device-side: DSP reference delivery
- 23: Send Ref_{IDSP_1} via ServiceInfo over $Session$
- 24: // Owner-side: DSP retrieval and verification
- 25: $DSP_d \leftarrow Fetch(Ref_{IDSP_1})$
- 26: **if** $VerifySignature(DSP_d) = \text{False}$ **then**
- 27: **Abort** (Invalid DSP)
- 28: **end if**
- 29: $D_d \leftarrow ExtractDescriptors(DSP_d), D_d \subseteq \mathbb{D}_{sec}$
- 30: **Phase 5: Policy Translation and Enforcement**
- 31: $Policies \leftarrow Translate(D_d)$
- 32: Enforce($Policies$)
- 33: **Phase 6: Continuous Monitoring and Update**
- 34: **while** d is active **do**
- 35: **if** DSPUpdateAvailable(Ref_{IDSP_1}) **then**
- 36: $DSP_d \leftarrow Fetch(Ref_{IDSP_1})$
- 37: $D_d \leftarrow ExtractDescriptors(DSP_d), D_d \subseteq \mathbb{D}_{sec}$
- 38: $Policies \leftarrow Translate(D_d)$
- 39: UpdateEnforcement($Policies$)
- 40: **end if**
- 41: **end while**

Upon device acquisition, the operator is granted access to the corresponding $IDSP_1$ through the DSP platform. This enables the operator domain to retrieve the security passport associated with the device, establishing the initial linkage between the manufacturing context and the operational environment.

4.4.2 Phase 2 – Discovery and redirection (TO0–TO1)

When first powered on in the field, the device has no prior knowledge of its target operational environment. This phase ensures that devices can be dynamically bound to an operational domain without prior configuration, supporting late binding across heterogeneous deployment environments. FDO addresses this through a discovery process mediated by the rendezvous service.

Before device activation, the operator registers its Owner endpoint within the rendezvous infrastructure through the TO0 protocol. For this, he leverages onboarding-related information exposed through the $IDSP_1$, including references to FDO trust artifacts such as the Ownership Voucher. This design allows onboarding metadata to be accessed through a unified DSP interface while preserving compatibility with the FDO protocol.

Upon boot, the device initiates the discovery process by contacting the rendezvous service using its onboard credentials and rendezvous information. During the TO1 protocol, the rendezvous service assists in device redirection by returning the address of the appropriate Owner endpoint.

This interaction, depicted in Figure 4, highlights the separation between discovery and trust establishment, where the rendezvous service only facilitates redirection without participating in secure provisioning.

4.4.3 Phase 3 – Ownership transfer and secure channel establishment (TO2)

The device connects to the Owner server and executes the TO2 protocol. During this phase, mutual authentication is performed based on device credentials and ownership evidence, resulting in the establishment of a secure and encrypted communication channel between the device and the operator domain. As illustrated in Figure 4, this phase establishes the trust boundary between the device and the operator domain, enabling subsequent secure metadata exchange. This secure channel also guarantees confidentiality and integrity for all subsequent exchanges, including the transmission of the DSP reference.

4.4.4 Phase 4 – DSP retrieval and verification

Once the secure channel is established, the device provides the DSP reference Ref_{IDSP_1} via the ServiceInfo exchange. As illustrated in Figure 4, this reference is received by the Owner Server and forwarded to the DSP Manager, which retrieves the corresponding passport from the DSP platform.

The retrieved DSP is then validated (Equation 8) to ensure its integrity and authenticity. If verification fails, the onboarding process is aborted, preventing the device from reaching an operational state (line 27 of Algorithm 1). After successful verification, the DSP Manager may extract a set of security descriptors from external repositories referenced within the DSP , including component inventories, behavioral policies, or vulnerability information. As shown in Figure 4, this may trigger additional interactions with manufacturer-hosted repositories (e.g., MUD servers) to retrieve authoritative policy definitions associated with the device.

This behavior is enabled by the reference-based design of the DSP, where only a lightweight identifier to $IDSP_1$ is exchanged during onboarding, while the retrieval and processing of potentially large descriptors (e.g., MUD, SBOM) are delegated to operator-side components. This design avoids

overloading resource-constrained devices and ensures that descriptor size does not impact the onboarding protocol. 736
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4.4.5 Phase 5 – Policy translation and enforcement 738

The extracted descriptors are processed within the operator domain by the Policy Manager, as depicted in Figure 4. This component acts as the central decision point, aggregating security inputs and translating high-level security intents into enforceable configurations. 739
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In particular, policy translation follows a multi-stage process in which abstract descriptors (e.g., MUD rules or security constraints) are first normalized into an intermediate representation, Medium-level Security Policy Language (MSPL), and then converted into infrastructure-specific or device-specific configurations. These may include network-level rules (e.g., ACLs, SDN flow rules) or device-level actions (e.g., configuration updates). 742
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The resulting policies are enforced through dedicated enforcement components, which may operate at the infrastructure level (e.g., gateways, switches) or at the device level via a local policy enforcer. This distributed enforcement model ensures that the device transitions directly into a controlled, least-privilege operational state immediately after onboarding. 747
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4.4.6 Phase 6 – Continuous monitoring and update 751

After onboarding, the DSP Manager periodically interacts with the DSP platform to detect updates to the associated $IDSP_1$, as shown in Figure 4. When updates are identified, the corresponding descriptors are retrieved, reprocessed, and the resulting policies are updated accordingly. 752
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This continuous interaction enables the system to maintain an up-to-date security posture throughout the device lifecycle. In particular, changes in the DSP may reflect updated configurations, newly available security information, or mitigation actions for emerging threats. In such cases, previously established policies can be dynamically revised or revoked. 755
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Furthermore, if a device is reassigned or transferred to a different operational domain, the FDO protocol inherently supports re-onboarding through a new ownership transfer process, allowing the device to be securely provisioned under a new trust context. 759
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Overall, this phase extends onboarding into a continuous lifecycle management process, ensuring alignment between device behavior and evolving security requirements. 762
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5 Security Analysis 764

This section analyzes the security properties of the proposed FDO–DSP onboarding approach, focusing on the threat model and the resistance to common attacks across IoT layers. The analysis is grounded on the architecture and workflow defined in Sections 4.3 and 4.4. 765
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This analysis does not include formal verification of the protocol composition between FDO and DSP. Instead, it builds on the established security properties of FDO and complements them with descriptor validation and policy enforcement mechanisms. 768
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5.1 Threat Model and Assumptions 771

The threat model considers a distributed IoT deployment in which devices, networks, and intermediary services may be exposed to adversarial actions. The attacker is assumed to have network-level capabilities, including eavesdropping, message injection, and replay, and may attempt to impersonate legitimate entities 772
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or tamper with exchanged data during the onboarding process. The security analysis is based on the following assumptions:

- devices are equipped with a hardware root of trust and securely store onboarding credentials;
- the FDO protocol correctly provides mutual authentication and secure channel establishment;
- DSP instances are integrity-protected through digital signatures and can be verified upon retrieval;
- the operator domain correctly enforces the derived security policies

5.2 Resistance to Common Attacks

The proposed approach mitigates relevant security threats across different layers of the IoT system by combining FDO-based secure onboarding with DSP-driven verification and policy enforcement.

Device layer. At the device level, the main threat is device spoofing or identity impersonation. This is mitigated through FDO mutual authentication during the TO2 phase, where only devices possessing valid credentials and ownership evidence can establish a secure session with the Owner. The use of hardware-backed secure storage further protects device credentials against extraction and misuse. This also mitigates credential misuse scenarios, as sensitive material is protected against extraction and unauthorized replication.

Network layer. At the communication level, threats include man-in-the-middle (MITM), replay, and eavesdropping attacks. The TO2 protocol establishes an authenticated and encrypted channel, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of all exchanged data, including the DSP reference transmitted via ServiceInfo. Replay attacks are prevented through freshness guarantees, such as nonces and session-based exchanges defined in the FDO protocol. Additionally, the secure channel prevents message injection and manipulation attacks.

Application and service layer. At the management level, risks include tampering with security descriptors and unauthorized modification of device configuration. DSP instances are digitally signed and verified upon retrieval (Phase 4). Any modification of the DSP or its metadata results in verification failure and aborts the onboarding process. This prevents attackers from exploiting the onboarding phase to introduce malicious or altered security metadata. Additionally, security policies derived from the DSP are enforced immediately after onboarding, preventing devices from operating with excessive privileges.

Intermediary services. The rendezvous service is treated as a minimally trusted component. It only performs discovery and redirection functions and does not participate in authentication or access sensitive data. As a result, even if compromised, it cannot impersonate the Owner or gain control over the onboarding process.

Cross-layer. Security policies derived from the DSP are enforced immediately after onboarding, eliminating the common exposure window in which devices operate without restrictions. This ensures that devices transition directly into a controlled, least-privilege state. Furthermore, the reference-based design of the DSP enables continuous policy updates during operation, allowing the system to adapt to newly discovered vulnerabilities and evolving security requirements throughout the device lifecycle.

5.3 Limitations of the Security Model

While the proposed approach provides strong guarantees for secure onboarding and policy enforcement, several limitations must be acknowledged.

The security model relies on the assumption of a trusted computing base, including the correctness of the FDO protocol implementation, the integrity of the DSP platform, and the proper enforcement of policies within the operator domain. Compromise of any of these components may impact the overall

Table 1: Overview of threats and mitigation mechanisms

Layer	Threat	Mitigation
Device	Device spoofing / impersonation	FDO mutual authentication (TO2), hardware-backed credential storage
Network	Man-in-the-Middle (MITM) Replay attacks Eavesdropping Message injection / manipulation	Authenticated and encrypted channel (TO2) Nonces and session-based freshness guarantees in FDO Encrypted communication channel (TO2) Integrity protection via authenticated secure channel (TO2)
Application / Service	Descriptor tampering Unauthorized access / over-privilege	DSP signature verification before processing Immediate policy enforcement after onboarding
Intermediary services	Compromised rendezvous	Minimal trust design, no role in authentication or provisioning
Cross-layer	Post-onboarding temporal gap Vulnerability exploitation / evolving threats	Immediate policy enforcement at onboarding Dynamic updates via DSP (e.g., MUD, Threat MUD)

security guarantees. Also, the approach assumes the presence of hardware-backed secure storage on the device. Devices lacking such capabilities may be more vulnerable to credential extraction or tampering. The model does not explicitly address physical attacks against devices beyond the protection offered by secure elements. Advanced physical tampering or side-channel attacks remain out of scope. Finally, while the system enables rapid mitigation through dynamic policy updates, its effectiveness depends on the timely availability and distribution of updated descriptors (e.g., MUD or Threat MUD). Delays in update propagation may temporarily expose devices to known vulnerabilities.

6 Experimental Validation

This section presents the experimental validation of the proposed model-driven secure onboarding approach. The evaluation considers a realistic Smart Home scenario to assess both the feasibility of integrating DSP within the FDO onboarding process and the impact of this integration on performance and policy enforcement. The validation focuses on two main aspects: (i) onboarding performance and associated overhead, and (ii) responsiveness to security updates during operation.

6.1 Scenario Description

The experimental validation is conducted in a heterogeneous Smart Home environment designed to reflect realistic IoT deployment conditions. The setup includes multiple platforms and device configurations to evaluate the proposed model-driven onboarding approach under diverse operational settings. The environment comprises typical IoT components such as sensors, actuators, and a centralized control platform.

Home Assistant [26] is used as the main orchestration platform, acting as the central point for device management and policy enforcement. It exposes a REST-based interface through which security policies derived from DSP descriptors are enforced, enabling integration without requiring modifications to device firmware. The FDO device functionality is integrated into Home Assistant through its add-on mechanism [27]. Home Assistant applications (add-ons) are containerized services managed by the underlying operating system. In this work, the FDO client is packaged as a custom add-on available in [28], allowing it to run natively within the platform and interact with other system components. This approach enables seamless integration of the onboarding process within an existing IoT ecosystem without requiring external deployment or manual configuration.

The implemented prototype follows the architecture defined in Section 4.3. FDO components (Rendezvous and Owner servers) are deployed as modular services, while the DSP platform is implemented

as a microservices-based system exposing REST-based APIs for DSP storage, retrieval, and lifecycle management. The DSPP acts as a central trust broker, supporting both generic and instance-level DSP management, and enabling controlled access to DSP documents through authentication and access control mechanisms. Its architecture separates API mediation, business logic, and data access into independently deployable services, facilitating scalability and modularity.

The prototype combines open-source components and custom microservices. The FDO protocol relies on the reference implementation provided by the FIDO Alliance [29], while the DSP Manager and Policy Manager are implemented as lightweight Python-based services. All components are deployed as containerized services using Docker, enabling modularity and isolation. The evaluation environment simulates the different architectural domains through isolated virtual networks, allowing reproducible execution of the FDO phases (DI, TO1, TO2) and DSP-based interactions. During manufacturing, devices are provisioned with FDO credentials and associated with a device-specific passport ($IDSP_1$), embedding a reference (Ref_{IDSP_1}) for retrieval during onboarding. The DSPs used are available in [30]. To assess the impact of descriptor retrieval on the onboarding process, two deployment configurations for the MUD server are considered. In the first configuration, MUD profiles are hosted on a public cloud storage service, representing a realistic external deployment scenario. In the second configuration, MUD profiles are served from a local Python-based server. This allows isolating the effect of external infrastructure latency and evaluating the intrinsic overhead of the proposed approach.

The evaluation is conducted across multiple deployments, all running Home Assistant as the control platform:

- a Smart Home pilot deployment at CERTH [31] using Home Assistant Green (Raspberry Pi Compute Module 4),
- a local deployment on Raspberry Pi 4B,
- a virtualized deployment using Proxmox, and
- a generic Linux-based device (AMD Ryzen, 64GB)

This heterogeneous setup allows assessing the behavior of the system across both resource-constrained edge platforms and more powerful virtualized environments. Finally, the evaluation includes a comparison with a manual onboarding and configuration process, providing insight into the practical benefits of the proposed approach in terms of automation and reduction of operational effort.

6.2 Phase-level Analysis

For the evaluation, we consider the total onboarding time and a phase-level analysis of the onboarding workflow. In particular, we measure the latency of the main FDO phases (DI, TO1, TO2), as well as the additional steps introduced by the proposed approach, including DSP retrieval, descriptor processing, policy generation, and enforcement. We can decompose the onboarding process as follows:

$$T_{onboarding} = T_{DI} + T_{TO1} + T_{TO2} + T_{DSP} + T_{MUD} + T_{policygen} + T_{policyenf}$$

where T_{DI} , T_{TO1} , T_{TO2} correspond to the FDO phases, T_{DSP} captures DSP retrieval and validation, T_{MUD} includes descriptor resolution and retrieval, and $T_{policygen}$, $T_{policyenf}$ represent policy generation and enforcement, respectively. In addition, we measure the update detection latency T_{update} during operation, defined as the time required to obtain and apply updates to the DSP once they become available. This decomposition allows isolating the contribution of each phase and analyzing the impact of DSP integration.

Figure 5 presents a detailed breakdown of the onboarding process across all evaluated deployments, distinguishing between configurations where descriptors are retrieved from a cloud-based repository and from a local server.

Figure 5: Phase level analysis of FDO-DSP in seconds

The results show that the FDO protocol phases (DI, TO1, and TO2) dominate the onboarding process in all configurations, accounting for the largest portion of the total latency. These phases remain consistent across deployments, although slightly lower execution times are observed in more powerful environments (e.g., Proxmox and Linux-based platforms) compared to resource-constrained devices such as Raspberry Pi or Home Assistant Green. This behavior is expected, as these phases involve cryptographic operations and protocol exchanges that benefit from increased computational resources.

The additional phases introduced by the proposed approach remain lightweight and stable. DSP retrieval is highly consistent across all deployments, with an average latency of approximately 0.67 seconds, confirming that the integration of DSP does not introduce significant overhead. Similarly, policy generation and enforcement phases are negligible, as they involve lightweight processing and simple configuration actions (e.g., triggering Home Assistant automations via webhook).

The main source of variability is observed in the descriptor-related phases, particularly MUD resolution and retrieval. When descriptors are hosted in a cloud environment, these phases introduce a significant delay (approximately 3-4 seconds), which substantially impacts the overall onboarding time. In contrast, when a REST MUD server is used, this latency is reduced to the order of milliseconds, resulting in a much more compact onboarding profile. This clearly indicates that the dominant overhead is not intrinsic to the proposed FDO-DSP integration, but rather depends on external infrastructure and network conditions. Across all deployments, the relative behavior of the phases remains consistent, demonstrating that the approach scales across heterogeneous environments while preserving predictable performance characteristics.

Finally, the update phase (T_{update}) reflects the time required to retrieve, process, and re-enforce updated DSP descriptors once they become available. The measured latency ranges between approximately 4.71 and 5.41 seconds across deployments. Although the system relies on a polling mechanism to detect updates, the polling interval is a configurable parameter and is therefore excluded from the reported measurements. As such, T_{update} captures only the effective processing time, confirming that dynamic updates can be applied efficiently without introducing significant overhead during operation.

6.3 Comparative evaluation

To provide a comprehensive evaluation, we combine a quantitative comparison against baseline and manual approaches with a qualitative assessment of existing onboarding solutions.

6.3.1 Experimental Comparison

A direct experimental comparison with alternative onboarding approaches is challenging due to differences in implementation models, infrastructure dependencies, and the lack of publicly available and comparable implementations. Therefore, the evaluation focuses on a controlled comparison between baseline FDO, the proposed FDO-DSP integration, and a manual onboarding approach, allowing us to isolate the overhead introduced by structured metadata processing and policy enforcement, as well as to assess the benefits of automation compared to manual onboarding approaches.

Figure 6 summarizes the total onboarding time across all evaluated deployments. The results show that the overhead introduced by FDO-DSP remains consistent across platforms in absolute terms, ranging between 4.72 and 5.41 seconds when descriptors are retrieved from a cloud-based repository. This indicates that the additional latency is largely independent of the underlying hardware and primarily associated with descriptor retrieval and processing.

In relative terms, the overhead varies from approximately 29.90% in resource-constrained environments (e.g., Home Assistant Green) up to 197.35% in high-performance platforms. However, this variation is mainly due to the significantly lower baseline onboarding time in more powerful systems, rather than an increase in the intrinsic cost of the proposed approach.

It is worth noting that when descriptors are retrieved from a local REST-based server, the overhead is reduced to less than 1 second (approximately 0.67-0.69 seconds), corresponding to less than 25% even in optimized environments. This indicates that the intrinsic overhead of DSP integration is minimal, and that the dominant cost observed in cloud-based deployments is driven by external infrastructure rather than by the onboarding mechanism itself.

From a system perspective, this overhead is incurred only once during the onboarding phase. In return, the proposed approach enables immediate enforcement of security policies at bootstrap time, eliminating the need for post-deployment configuration. This significantly reduces the exposure window in which devices operate without restrictions, a well-known security risk in conventional onboarding approaches.

Therefore, the overhead should be interpreted as a bounded and largely network-dependent cost that enables secure-by-design deployment. The trade-off is favorable: a small increase in onboarding time results in stronger security guarantees, automated policy enforcement, and elimination of manual configuration steps. These findings are consistent with prior work in IoT onboarding and provisioning, where the integration of additional security mechanisms introduces moderate but acceptable latency in exchange for improved security and manageability [12,16].

Finally, manual onboarding provides a useful reference point to contextualize the benefits of automation. In the evaluated scenario, manual onboarding and policy configuration require approximately 2330 seconds, which is substantially higher than the automated approaches. Manual results are not included in Figure 6, as their magnitude would distort the scale and limit the readability of the comparison. Nevertheless, this gap clearly illustrates the substantial reduction in deployment time and operational effort achieved through the proposed approach, while simultaneously improving security guarantees.

Figure 6: FDO vs FDO-DSP time comparison (seconds)

6.3.2 Comparison with Existing Approaches

While the previous subsection provides a quantitative assessment based on experimental results, we complement this analysis with a qualitative comparison (Table 2) of existing IoT onboarding approaches and our proposal. This comparison considers key architectural and security dimensions, highlighting trade-offs between simplicity, scalability, and security integration, and positioning the proposed approach within the state of the art.

In terms of onboarding automation and scalability, manual approaches provide no automation and do not scale beyond small deployments. User-assisted mechanisms such as Wi-Fi DPP and ASOP improve usability but still depend on human interaction, resulting in medium scalability at best. In contrast, BRSKI, AWS IoT, and FDO achieve high levels of automation through zero-touch or fully automated provisioning, making them suitable for large-scale environments [32]. FDO-DSP inherits these properties from FDO, maintaining high scalability without introducing significant additional overhead. This is achieved through the reference-based design of the DSP, where security descriptors (e.g., SBOM, MUD, or vulnerability data) are not embedded but accessed via external references. During onboarding, only a lightweight DSP reference (e.g., a URL) is exchanged, while the retrieval and processing of security descriptors is performed by the DSP manager within the operator domain. As a result, resource-constrained IoT devices are not required to process large security artifacts, and the onboarding process remains lightweight and scalable even when descriptors are large or complex.

Regarding identity and credential management, approaches vary significantly in structure and flexibility. Manual provisioning relies on static or ad-hoc credentials, while ASOP uses pre-shared symmetric keys and DPP employs public key bootstrapping mechanisms. BRSKI and AWS IoT adopt PKI-based models, providing strong identity guarantees but introducing dependencies on manufacturer-issued credentials or cloud infrastructures [14]. FDO offers a more flexible model based on ownership vouchers and cryptographic identities, enabling the decoupling of device identity from its operational domain [32]. FDO-DSP preserves this model, ensuring compatibility while extending its capabilities.

This flexibility is further reflected in late binding support. Most approaches, including DPP, ASOP, and AWS IoT, bind devices to a specific domain or infrastructure during initial provisioning. BRSKI provides limited flexibility through voucher-based mechanisms, but remains anchored to manufacturer-issued identities [4]. In contrast, FDO fully supports late binding, allowing ownership transfer and dynamic

association at deployment time. FDO-DSP maintains this capability, making it suitable for dynamic and multi-stakeholder supply chain scenarios.

The differences become more pronounced when considering metadata exchange. Manual onboarding does not support metadata, while DPP and ASOP provide only limited capabilities, typically restricted to basic device information and bootstrapping data (e.g., identifiers, credentials, or network configuration parameters). BRSKI enables limited information exchange through enrollment protocols, primarily focused on certificate-based identity establishment and ownership validation via MASA-issued vouchers, rather than supporting the integration of structured security metadata. In contrast, AWS IoT supports richer metadata through cloud-managed attributes, allowing devices to be associated with descriptive information such as configuration parameters, identifiers, and policy attachments within a centralized infrastructure [33]. FDO allows the secure transfer of onboarding data, but does not impose a structure on such information. FDO-DSP extends this capability by introducing structured metadata, enabling consistent representation and interpretation of security-relevant information across systems.

This distinction has direct implications for policy enforcement. As shown in Table 2, most approaches provide limited or no support for enforcing policies during onboarding. Even in BRSKI, enforcement is indirect and typically tied to PKI-based mechanisms, while AWS IoT provides strong policy enforcement through tightly integrated cloud services. FDO, despite supporting data transfer, does not define how policies should be derived or enforced. In contrast, FDO-DSP enables strong policy enforcement by linking structured onboarding information with enforcement mechanisms, allowing policies to be applied as part of the onboarding process rather than as a separate step.

A similar pattern is observed in supply chain ownership tracking. Manual, DPP, and ASOP approaches do not provide mechanisms for tracking ownership across entities, while BRSKI and AWS IoT offer only limited capabilities tied to their respective trust models. FDO introduces partial support through ownership transfer, but does not explicitly represent ownership evolution. FDO-DSP extends this capability by enabling full and explicit tracking of ownership and associated security context throughout the device lifecycle.

From an infrastructure perspective, manual approaches require no dedicated components, while DPP and ASOP depend on local configurators or backend services. BRSKI requires a full PKI and registrar infrastructure, and AWS IoT depends on a cloud platform. FDO introduces a modular architecture based on rendezvous and ownership services, avoiding tight coupling to specific infrastructures. FDO-DSP builds on this architecture, adding support for descriptor processing without altering the underlying deployment model.

Finally, platform dependency remains low for most approaches except AWS IoT, which is tightly coupled to its cloud ecosystem. Both FDO and FDO-DSP maintain low dependency, preserving interoperability across heterogeneous environments.

Overall, the table shows that existing onboarding approaches typically optimize for specific dimensions, resulting in inherent trade-offs. Manual and user-assisted approaches (e.g., DPP and ASOP) prioritize simplicity and ease of deployment, but offer limited automation and scalability. PKI-based and cloud-driven solutions such as BRSKI and AWS IoT provide stronger identity management and policy enforcement capabilities, although often at the cost of increased infrastructure complexity or platform dependency. FDO achieves a balanced approach, combining automation, scalability, and deployment flexibility through mechanisms such as late binding and ownership transfer. However, it does not natively address the integration of structured security metadata or policy enforcement during onboarding. FDO-DSP builds on these strengths by incorporating structured metadata, enabling automated policy enforcement, and supporting full supply chain tracking. In addition, it enables the dynamic update of security policies

Table 2: Comparison of onboarding approaches with FDO-DSP

Feature	Manual	Wi-Fi DPP	ASOP	BRSKI	AWS IoT	FDO	FDO-DSP
Automation/ Scalability	None	Medium (user-assisted)	Medium (user-assisted)	High (zero touch)	High (automated)	High (zero touch)	High (zero touch)
Identity and Credential Management	Static/none	Public key + QR	PSK	PKI (X.509, IDevID)	Cloud managed PKI (X.509)	PKI-like + OV	PKI-like + OV
Late binding	No	No	No	Limited	No	Yes	Yes
Metadata exchange	No	Network parameters	Partial	Limited	Yes	Yes	Yes (structured and updatable)
Policy enforcement	Manual (post)	No	No	No	Automated (post)	No	Automated in onboarding
Ownership tracking	No	No	No	MASA based	Partial (cloud registry)	OV chain	OV chain
Platform dependency	Tooling dependent	Open (Wi-Fi Alliance)	Low (open+Google)	Open (IETF)	High (cloud)	Open (multivendor)	Open (multivendor)

after onboarding through the continuous retrieval and processing of DSP information by the management infrastructure. This provides a more comprehensive and lifecycle-aware solution for secure IoT onboarding.

6.3.3 Comparison with existing security descriptors

While the previous comparison focuses on onboarding mechanisms, it is also important to analyze how different security descriptor models represent and integrate security-related information. To this end, Table 3 compares representative security descriptor models in terms of their expressive capabilities and integration potential. Existing approaches are typically domain-specific: SBOM focuses on component inventories, VEX/VDR on vulnerability disclosure, MUD on network behavior, and Threat MUD on mitigation actions. OSCAL provides a structured framework for compliance and assessment. In contrast, DSP adopts a unified device-centric model that integrates these perspectives, enabling a more comprehensive representation of security-relevant information across the device lifecycle.

Regarding *vulnerability description*, VEX/VDR and OSCAL provide explicit mechanisms to represent vulnerabilities and their status. SBOM formats may include vulnerability information through extensions (e.g., CycloneDX [34]), but this capability is not consistently supported across all specifications. Threat MUD offers only partial support through references to threat identifiers (e.g., CVEs) and severity indicators (e.g., CVSS), without modeling vulnerabilities as structured entities [35]. In contrast, DSP incorporates vulnerability descriptors through structured references to external artifacts (e.g., VEX/VDR), enabling consistent integration within a broader security context. For *behavior specification*, MUD and Threat MUD natively define network communication patterns, whereas OSCAL provides only descriptive, non-enforceable representations. DSP supports behavior through policy-based specifications that can be directly linked to enforcement mechanisms, while SBOM and VEX/VDR do not include behavioral modeling capabilities. For *mitigation definition*, Threat MUD explicitly encodes mitigation actions that can be directly enforced at the network level and OSCAL supports remediation planning through structured constructs within its assessment and compliance models [11]. VEX and VDR provide partial support, as some formats (e.g., CSAF-based VEX [36]) include remediation or mitigation information, while others (e.g., OpenVEX [37]) focus solely on vulnerability status without explicitly modeling mitigation actions. MUD offers only indirect support, as mitigation strategies can be approximated by restricting communication patterns, although such behavior is not explicitly represented as a mitigation construct within the model. In contrast, DSP enables explicit representation of mitigation strategies and their association with vulnerabilities and risks through structured descriptors and linked artifacts.

Table 3: Comparison of security descriptor models

Feature	SBOM	VEX/VDR	MUD	Threat MUD	OSCAL	DSP
Primary focus	Components	Vulnerabilities	Network behavior	Mitigation	Compliance	Unified device security
Vulnerability description	Partial	Explicit	None	Partial	Explicit	Explicit (via VEX/VDR)
Behavior specification	None	None	Native	Native	Descriptive	Policy-based
Mitigation definition	None	Partial	Implicit	Explicit	Explicit	Explicit
External referencing	Limited	Supported	Supported	Supported	Supported	Supported
Multi-descriptor integration	Limited	None	Limited	None	Limited	Native
Policy enforcement support	None	None	Network-level	Network-level	None	Fully supported

With respect to *external referencing*, most models support links to external documentation. This capability is supported in VEX/VDR and threat MUD (e.g., links to vulnerability databases), but also in MUD (e.g., links to documentation or SBOM), OSCAL, and DSP, while SBOM typically embeds information locally. However, some SBOM formats (e.g., CycloneDX [34]) allow more flexibility to embed external information. A key differentiating feature is *multi-descriptor integration*. Existing approaches provide limited or no support for combining heterogeneous security descriptors within a unified model. While some formats allow references to external artifacts, they rely on loose coupling rather than structured integration. In contrast, DSP provides native support for integrating multiple descriptor types within a single, consistent representation. Finally, *policy enforcement support* highlights whether descriptors can be translated into operational controls. MUD and Threat MUD support enforcement at the network level [38], whereas SBOM, VEX/VDR, and OSCAL are primarily descriptive. DSP extends this capability by enabling full policy enforcement driven by integrated security descriptors.

This capability aligns with emerging regulatory frameworks such as the EU CRA [6], which emphasize secure-by-default operation, vulnerability management, and continuous security updates. A detailed mapping between DSP capabilities and CRA requirements is provided in [10].

7 Discussion

The results presented in Section 6 demonstrate the feasibility of integrating DSP-driven security descriptors within a secure onboarding workflow based on FDO. Beyond functional validation, the approach reframes onboarding as a control point for enforcing security-by-default, rather than solely as a mechanism for identity establishment.

A first key observation is that the proposed approach reduces the temporal gap between device provisioning and policy enforcement identified in Section 2. In contrast to conventional workflows, where policies are applied after connectivity is established, policy enforcement in the proposed model occurs immediately after onboarding. From a performance perspective, the integration introduces a bounded and predictable latency, ranging between approximately 4.72 and 5.41 seconds in cloud-based deployments. The phase-level analysis shows that this overhead is dominated by descriptor retrieval, particularly MUD resolution, rather than by the DSP model itself. When descriptors are served locally, the overhead drops below one second (approximately 0.67 seconds), confirming that the intrinsic cost of DSP integration is low. This indicates that the overhead is primarily driven by infrastructure locality and deployment conditions. Moreover, this cost is incurred only once during onboarding and does not affect runtime operation.

A second relevant outcome is the ability to externalize and reuse security descriptors independently of the onboarding protocol. The DSP provides a unified and machine-readable representation that enables the coordinated use of heterogeneous artifacts (e.g., SBOM, MUD, VEX/VDR) during onboarding. By adopting a reference-based design, the approach avoids embedding large descriptors in the onboarding exchange,

limiting device-side processing to lightweight identifiers. This may be beneficial in resource-constrained environments, where transferring or parsing full descriptors would introduce additional overhead. Instead, descriptor retrieval and processing are delegated to the operator domain, reducing device complexity while preserving flexibility and enabling reuse across lifecycle stages. This design also supports continuous security management, as updates can be retrieved, processed, and enforced in approximately 5 seconds. As a result, onboarding can act as the entry point of a lifecycle-aware process, in contrast to existing approaches that remain largely static after provisioning.

From an operational perspective, the comparison with manual onboarding highlights a substantial reduction in deployment effort. While the automated approach introduces a moderate latency overhead with respect to FDO, it reduces provisioning time from minutes to seconds and eliminates manual policy configuration. This may be relevant in large-scale deployments, where manual processes introduce scalability limitations and increase the risk of configuration errors.

At the same time, the findings highlight several limitations that affect the applicability of the approach. The reliance on external descriptor repositories introduces a dependency on network availability and service responsiveness. As observed in the evaluation, descriptor retrieval can become the dominant source of latency, particularly in cloud-based deployments. While this can be mitigated through caching or edge deployment strategies, it remains an architectural consideration that must be addressed in real-world scenarios. Additionally, the effectiveness of the approach depends on the quality and completeness of the underlying security descriptors. The DSP model assumes that artifacts such as SBOMs, MUD profiles, or VEX statements are accurate and up to date. In practice, inconsistencies, missing information, or delayed updates may limit the reliability of the resulting policies. This challenge is not specific to the proposed solution, but becomes more critical as policy enforcement is automated and tightly coupled to descriptor content. Moreover, the current implementation relies on predefined mappings between abstract policy representations and concrete enforcement mechanisms. While this is sufficient in controlled environments, it may limit flexibility in heterogeneous or highly dynamic systems where enforcement capabilities vary across devices and infrastructures. Extending the approach toward more adaptive or context-aware policy translation remains an open challenge.

Overall, the results indicate that integrating structured security models such as the DSP with secure onboarding protocols enables a more consistent and integrated approach to device provisioning and policy enforcement, reducing the gap between these processes while maintaining practical performance.

8 Conclusion and Future Work

This work presented a model-driven approach to secure IoT onboarding by integrating the DSP with the FDO protocol. The proposed solution bridges the gap between onboarding and policy enforcement. It enables the retrieval and activation of security descriptors during the onboarding phase, ensuring that devices are deployed in a constrained and policy-compliant state. The DSP was formally defined as a lifecycle-aware model inspired by OSCAL, capable of aggregating heterogeneous security descriptors (e.g., SBOM, MUD, VEX/VDR) through a reference-based structure. Its integration with FDO enables a secure binding between device identity and its associated security metadata, supporting both initial provisioning and continuous adaptation during operation. Experimental results demonstrate the feasibility of the approach, showing that DSP integration introduces a moderate and bounded overhead while enabling immediate policy enforcement and contributing to improved security at deployment time.

Future work will focus on extending the evaluation to large-scale and heterogeneous IoT environments, further assessing scalability and performance under diverse conditions. In addition, the potential use of

Large Language Models (LLMs) will be explored to support automated analysis and interpretation of security requirements. In particular, future research will investigate how LLMs can be leveraged to map regulatory or standard-based requirements to DSP representations, enabling automated compliance assessment and the generation of validation tests based on device security descriptors. Finally, future work will explore the integration of additional security descriptors and contextual information to support more adaptive and context-aware policy enforcement during onboarding.

Acknowledgement: The authors would like to thank Miguel Fernández Llamas for his support in the development of the graphical interface used to facilitate timing measurements and policy enforcement management.

Funding Statement: The work has been produced with the support of a 2024 Leonardo Grant for Scientific Research and Cultural Creation, BBVA Foundation. The Foundation takes no responsibility for the opinions, statements and contents of this project, which are entirely the responsibility of its authors. Research also partially supported by the EU through the Horizon research and innovation program DOSS (grant agreement no. 101120270) and COBALT (grant agreement no. 101119602).

Author Contributions: The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: Conceptualization, Sara Matheu, Pedro Ruzafa, Antonio Skarmeta and Dionysios Kehagias; methodology, Sara Matheu, Pedro Ruzafa; software, Pedro Ruzafa and Ilias Kalouptsoglou; validation, Pedro Ruzafa and Ilias Kalouptsoglou; formal analysis, Sara Matheu; investigation, Sara Matheu, Pedro Ruzafa; resources, Pedro Ruzafa and Ilias Kalouptsoglou; data curation, Pedro Ruzafa and Ilias Kalouptsoglou; writing—original draft preparation, Sara Matheu, Pedro Ruzafa and Ilias Kalouptsoglou; writing—review and editing, Sara Matheu; visualization, Sara Matheu; supervision, Sara Matheu and Antonio Skarmeta; project administration, Sara Matheu, Antonio Skarmeta and Dionysios Kehagias; funding acquisition, Sara Matheu, Antonio Skarmeta and Dionysios Kehagias. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Availability of Data and Materials: Data openly available in <https://github.com/saranieves92/DSP>.

Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

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AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ASOP	Agile Secure Onboarding Protocol
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BOM	Bill of Materials
BRSKI	Bootstrapping Remote Secure Key Infrastructure
CBOM	Cryptographic Bill of Materials
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
CPE	Common Platform Enumeration
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
DI	Device Initialization
DPP	Device Provisioning Protocol
DSP	Device Security Passport
DSPP	Device Security Passport Platform
ECC	Elliptic Curve Cryptography
ECISO	European Cyber Security Organisation
EU	European Union
FDO	FIDO Device Onboard
FEAM	Front-end Access Management
FIDO	Fast IDentity Online
GUID	Globally Unique Identifier
HBOM	Hardware Bill of Materials
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	Internet of Things
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Description
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NVD	National Vulnerability Database
LLM	Large Language Model
OSCAL	Open Security Controls Assessment Language
OV	Ownership Voucher
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
RV	Rendezvous
SCAP	Security Content Automation Protocol
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VDR	Vulnerability Disclosure Report
VEX	Vulnerability Exploitability eXchange
XCCDF	eXtensible Configuration Checklist Description Format

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